

Milestone 7 (M2.2) - extended version

Overview of legal documents required

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1. Executive Summary

Milestone Scope – Relevance to B1MGplus

The B1MGplus project supports the creation of a European cross-border network of genomic and clinical data to improve healthcare. The project provides coordination and support to the 1+ Million Genomes (1+MG) initiative. To support the 1+MG initiative, the B1MGplus project focuses on several objectives, one of which is to support the preparatory work for the creation and operation of a European Digital Infrastructure Consortium (EDIC).

As per the GA, the general objective of WP2 is to “provide input to the GDI Project and the Genome EDIC that is to be set up to support the EDIC in becoming operational. The work will provide the foundation (i.e. content creation) for the negotiations of member countries in the GDI Pillar I on the data governance and governance implementation, sustainability and business model as well as the input into the development of the IT infrastructure. The work will be limited to cover a minimum viable product that allows the Genome EDIC to become operational but not cover any future developments yet as these plans will be too volatile during the lifetime of the project and the provided funds not sufficient to cover additional scenarios.”

Within this framework, the DoA allocates to T2.3 the aim “Once the governance and data governance are finally decided” to help translating “the relationship between the various actors ... into standard legal documents enabling binding commitments and regulating the rights and obligations of all the entities **to the extent that they are not provided for in the statutes.**” (emphasis added). Accordingly, M2.2 is described as “List and scope of contracts and other legal documents that are necessary for operations.

In this context, the purpose of Milestone 2.2 is to identify the extent of the legal documents required to transform the Genomic Data Infrastructure into an EDIC, establish it and draw up its statutes.

To reach this aim, T2.3 needed first to identify the legal documents and content that must be addressed in the statutes and those that the governing body will need to address directly, once established and since the early implementation stages. The latter documents will require the expression of the full political and technical decision-making of the assembly of members pursuant to ar. 16 of the (DECISION (EU) 2022/2481 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 14 December 2022 establishing the Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030 – hereinafter also “DDDP”). Yet, T2.3 could contribute to identify the general scope of expected contracts to fulfil the needs of the procurement policy of the Genome EDIC since their specific content would be subject and dependant on national applicable law.

If time and resources will allow it, the scope of T2.3 could be expanded to help defining a general strategy in the content design of agreements or other relevant document among and with multiple “public entities, including regions or private entities with a public service mission” from the same participating Member State to ensure the MS participation is governed unitarily and in a harmonized way. Yet it must be stressed that the Statutes could only envisage obligations and rights in general harmonized terms, but it would necessarily be to each and every Member State to decide the forms (e.g. eventually not a contract but an interinstitutional agreement) actually used pursuant to the relevant national applicable law.

Work accomplished

Against this background, the development of the list of legal documents was achieved through studies of previous preparatory works of other EDICs and their statutes, looking at the experience of ERICs also with the help of interviews with existing and EDIC to be. A batch of interviews has been planned and partially executed under Chatham House rules.

Conclusion

The work conducted has led to a still prospective and non-final list of documents needed for the stabilisation of the EDIC, which will be explained in more detail in the following sections. Subsequently, the documents deemed necessary for this purpose will be divided into progressive ‘stages’, depending on whether they are to be drafted before or after the creation of the EDIC or by the EDIC itself. The study results have been confirmed so far by the interviews. Still since activities are ongoing and other interviews and research is planned the can be considered as contingently final.

2. Description of work accomplished

What has been done – Methodology

To develop the list of useful and necessary legal documents for the establishment of the EDIC, a study was undertaken based on the ‘methods’ of setting up other EDICs. To do this, Smartlex run an extensive study on previous experiences on setting up similar infrastructures (well beyond research infrastructures such as ERICS) and contacted representatives of EDICs to obtain information about their experience in: preparing and setting up an institution; creating

the Statutes and related documents; selecting the most relevant legal documents to achieve the goal of creating an EDIC.

In particular, Smartlex contacted and has partially run a first round of interviews:

- Alliance for Language Technologies European Digital Infrastructure Consortium (ALT-EDIC) (<https://www.alt-edic.eu/>)
- CitiVERSE (<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/factpages/citiverse>)
- EDIC for European Blockchain Partnership and European Blockchain Service Infrastructure (EUROPEUM-EDIC) ([EUROPEUM-EDIC - EBSI -](#))

In order to better understand the legal documents used for the creation of EDICs, a series of questions were developed specifically for conducting the interviews (see Annex 1) as a template to guide the discussion for the interviews. The questions posed to the EDICs are contained in Annex 1 this Milestone.

The tentative results of the preparing work done by SLEX is submitted for discussion during the interviews also to identify eventual gaps to be filled according to “real life” experiences . Since the interviews are planned under Chatham house rules no specific details of who has given which input can be provided in this document.

The content of the lessons learned during the interview exercise will be briefly outlined in the next section, immediately after the list of documents required for the stabilisation of an EDIC as reached during the study and as corroborated by the interviewees so far.

In the preparatory work important insights were also gained from the European Commission's EDIC User Guide and the statutes of existing EDICs.

Interaction with other tasks

Task 2.3 is closely related to 2.1, insofar as it too deals with analysing and resolving relevant issues concerning the creation and implementation of the new EDIC. It also benefited of the activities pursued for D2.8 and their insights.

Collaboration with external partners/projects

As already mentioned, the preparation of the Milestone required the participation of parties external to the project, namely representatives/delegates of the mentioned EDICs and a close relationship with the other entities working in the WP2, especially LNDS.

Continuous collaboration with the contacted EDICS is already under planning in continuing the relevant tasks in order to consolidate the list of documents required for the establishment of the EDIC.

3. Results: overview of legal documents required

From the studies conducted and interviews, it was possible for Smartlex to compile a list of potential legal documents whose general drafting is necessary for the establishment of the EDIC. It should be noted that the list of documents below cannot yet be considered final, as it

may be necessary to amend the list during the project work, e.g. by adding some documents or moving them from one stage to another.

It should be noted that, in the list of documents below, there is no reference to the sustainability plan, which, although a necessary document for the creation/establishment of an EDIC, falls under a different task than the one in which this Milestone is located.

Below follows the list:

a. Documents to be redacted before the constitution of the EDIC

- State of intent to participate by MS containing the Terms of Reference to govern the preparation phase
- Request to the Commission to set up the EDIC
- Technical description of the multi-Country project to be implemented by the EDIC
- Declaration by the host Member State whether it recognises the EDIC as an international body
- Draft Statute

b. Documents to be prepared after the establishment of the EDIC and left to the responsibility of the General Assembly

- Draft Implementing Rules to be submitted to the ruling body
- General Data Policy
- General Procurement Policy
- General Intellectual Property Rights Policy
- General Employment Policy, including equal opportunities
- Access Policy
- Dissemination Policy and “FAIRification”
- Guidelines for agreements for multiple participation from Member States

c. Documents useful in the medium term (after establishment)

- Intellectual Property Rights Policy implementation
- Data Management Policy
- Security Policy
- Risk Management
- Human Resources
- General scope of expected contracts to fulfil the needs of the procurement policy of the Genome EDIC

The above mentioned list and their distribution along different phases of development have been confirmed so far during the interview exercise. Discussion also emphasized the strategic importance of drafting clear policies as implementing documents under the Statute.

It was also confirmed that the only documents to be compulsory drafted before the establishment of an EDIC are those mentioned under a) above.

In addition to the documents, Smartlex was able, during the interview exercise, to elaborate on some of the challenges experienced by the representatives/delegates during its creation and establishment of the EDIC. They are mostly related to the difficulty of ensuring wide legal uniformity across the nodes due to national legislative differences and to maintain a clear information flow between legal and technical experts in the actual operation of the EDIC. These insights will be taken into account in the continuation of WP2 activities. The questions in Annex 1 were not asked one by one but were the starting point for a discussion by macro-theme (statute, mandatory documents, suggestions, etc.).

4. Conclusions & Impact

The work carried out as part of this Milestone has made it possible to gather and analyse a significant body of information useful for defining the legal aspects required for the establishment of the Genomics EDIC and to kick off the drafting process. Through the study of previous experiences of other EDICs and direct ongoing engagement with them, it was possible to draft an initial list of essential legal documents, divided according to the preparatory phases (pre- and post-establishment). Within this project only the first ones are assumed to be finalized.

Although the list is still evolving and may be subject to updates during the project, it already represents a solid and structured foundation on which to build the legal framework of the future EDIC.

5. Next steps

In the near future, Smartlex will continue to carry out the activities assigned to it within the project in cooperation with the other tasks and WPs, to consolidate the list of documents and, in general, the legal documents necessary for the implementation of the EDIC into a final vision.

In order to achieve this, Smartlex will continue to maintain contacts, discussions and interviews with existing and forthcoming EDICS.

6. References

- *European Digital Infrastructure Consortium User Guide*, European Commission, (2023). Available at: [European Digital Infrastructure Consortium \(EDIC\) | Shaping Europe's digital future](#).
- Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2024/458 of 1 February 2024 on setting up the European Digital Infrastructure Consortium for the Alliance for Language Technologies (ALT-EDIC). Available at: [Implementing decision - 2024/458 - EN - EUR-Lex](#).

- Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2024/1432 of 21 May 2024 on setting up the European Digital Infrastructure Consortium for European Blockchain Partnership and European Blockchain Service Infrastructure (EUROPEUM-EDIC). Available at: [Commission Implementing Decision \(EU\) 2024/1432 of 21 May 2024 setting up the European Digital Infrastructure Consortium for European Blockchain Partnership and European Blockchain Service Infrastructure \(EUROPEUM-EDIC\)](#).
- Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2024/459 of 1 February 2024 on setting up the European Digital Infrastructure Consortium for Networked Local Digital Twins towards the CitiVERSE (LDT CitiVERSE EDIC). Available at: [Implementing decision - 2024/459 - EN - EUR-Lex](#).
- Statutes for the EDIC on Alliance for Language Technologies (ALT-EDIC).
- Statutes for the EDIC on Networked Local Digital Twins towards the CitiVERSE.
- Statutes of the European Digital Infrastructure Consortium for European Blockchain Partnership and European Blockchain Service Infrastructure (EUROPEUM-EDIC)

Annex no.1: EDICs interview

Below are the elaborated questions for the EDIC interviews.

General questions.

- Have you developed an implementation strategy separate from the initial technical project?
- Have you adopted internal rules (implementing\operational rules) before the establishment of the EDIC or after?
- Were there any other binding documents produced in the start-up phase, such as internal regulations, codes of ethics, data protection policies, beyond those mandatory?

About legal documents and contracts.

- What kind of legal documents and/or contracts did you have to envisage to set up the EDIC before its formal establishment?
 - a. Are they forecast as necessary in your Statute?
 - b. Which documents were drafted before the establishment of the EDIC?
 - c. Which documents were prepared at a later stage?
- Are the documents (at least the main ones) listed in your operational rules (whatever name they take)?
- To what extent would you recommend including internal policies (procurement, access, IPR, etc.) already in the Statute?

Agreements between members.

- Have you signed a separate agreement between the members (e.g. Memorandum of Understanding or Membership Agreement) to regulate the internal aspects of setting up EDIC?

General suggestions.

- Are there any legal documents that you would include with hindsight if you were to set up an EDIC now?
- Does the EDIC plan to position itself as an intermediary for the purposes of data altruism/Data Governance Act?
- What suggestions would you give to those who want to set up EDIC today?

